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of **EXPRESSION**

A Creative Folio

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My Poor Ambitious Dad

(this is dedicated to my dad)

I'm young, fragile, and innocent
I play with kids around the house
My dad and I laugh aloud
His love and care I always hear

I grew up fast like snow that melts
I saw the hardship that life has given
I always fear my life ahead
My dad assured me my life was great

The hurdles now are getting high
My dad is smiling like life is good
But deep in his heart are fear and hope
He always says that life is great

I never think that he is weak
I only know when I saw him cry
Because of me, he forgets his pride
To provide my things to finish school

He wants to live like a princess at house
He smiles at us at our little success
He is poor, and nobody in the community
Now I have my own life, different from the past
I always owe it to my poor, ambitious dad